

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN SCIENCE TEACHING

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Annotation: In this article the composition of Natural Sciences, from the study of Sciences the goal is to apply interactive methods based on an innovative approach to teaching subjects

Keywords: Natural (SCIENCE) Sciences, "Innovation", "interactive methods", "innovative technologies", integration, "organizer" method, "Word top game," host " Method.

Introduction

Currently, natural sciences, which include natural sciences, are being introduced into the education system of Uzbekistan, starting from the 2021-2022 academic year, in grades 1-6. Natural sciences (SCIENCE) are taught simultaneously in grades 1-2. "The World Around Us" combines "Natural Science" in grades 3-4 and 4 separate subjects in high school, namely geography, biology, physics (from grade 6), chemistry (from grade 7).

The advantages and importance of natural sciences (SCIENCE) lie in the fact that through science the student comprehends the holistic, indivisible integrity of the world, forms a scientific worldview, and develops research skills. Natural sciences are sciences that study the substances that make up a person, his health, as well as the entire environment: soil, atmosphere, earth as a whole, space, nature, all living and nonliving objects and their changes.

The main task of the block module of natural and economic sciences is to cover a complex of scientific and practical knowledge about phenomena and processes occurring in nature, the stages of development of living organisms, the

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influence of humanity on the laws of nature and society. To the extent that a student's internal motivation is formed, what is important is his interest in the natural and economic sciences, understanding of environmental problems and the ability to make important decisions in solving them, as well as in analyzing the impact on the environment and the environment. social environment.

The mutual integration of sciences should lead students to an understanding of nature as a single being, a single view of the Universe. At the same time, students must understand the negative and positive impacts of human activities on nature, global environmental problems on a time and space scale, as well as a sense of responsibility towards nature. development of society.

Teaching natural sciences as a separate subject begins in the 1st grade. The educational material is combined into the topics "Natural bodies", "Flora and fauna", "Preserving health" and "Ecology". The natural sciences program allows younger schoolchildren to experience not only the beauty and richness of nature, but also the nature of our republic. When teaching natural sciences, attention is paid to the formation and expansion of the scientific and natural worldview of students, to a description of the topic of each lesson on teaching logical thinking. In the process of individual completion of tasks by students, their mental activity is activated, and confidence in their knowledge, strengths and abilities increases. As a result, each person develops to the level of his or her potential. In cognitive activity organized in this way, time is effectively used, and as a result, the effectiveness of learning increases. The cognitive activity of students is organized individually during lessons conducted using modern pedagogical teaching technologies.

"Organizer" method. This method helps create conditions for students to think freely and openly about issues (topics) and freely express their personal opinions. "Organizer" method - between different ideas requires identifying a framework for thinking about relationships. This method is a form of thinking that is not aimed at a specific object. Its use is carried out in connection with the principle of human

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brain activity. — The “Organizer” method is a type of branching in which not only primary or only secondary data, but also primary and secondary data remain open. Students must find information about this place, no matter what network is open. Information written by the teacher will help them with this. This method can be distributed to students on a separate sheet of paper or to the group on whatman paper. You can also check the completion of the task using the slides. The “Organizer” method is so convenient that it can be used in any subject of primary education. In grades 3-4, the use of the Organizer method expands as students' understanding of topics expands. The Organizer method can be used with students individually or in groups. In group learning, this method manifests itself as a set of ideas expressed by group members. This creates the opportunity to harmonize the ideas put forward by each group member and find connections between them.

Game "Find the word". This method can be used in all parts of the lesson.

The teacher says a word about birds, animals, fruits, vegetables, the students continue. The student must say a word that begins with the letter that ends with the word the teacher began.

For example: hedgehog - dragonfly - dog - bear - crow - bee - snake, etc. This method helps students think and answer quickly, and also strengthens memory.

The "Muserar" method. This method is a certain type of active activity designed to prevent indifference of students in the lesson, fatigue and mental pressure on students during the lesson. Therefore, they can be used to prevent the occurrence of “freezing” in the classroom, and if such “freezing” has formed, then with its help it can be used to melt and break it. Many teachers use “talkers” only at the initial stage of teaching, but they can be used with equal success during a lesson, when communication with students or between students for one reason or another becomes difficult. To what extent does a science teacher use these new educational methods and methods? In our opinion, some trainers use these methods ineffectively in classes. Informatization of society requires constant innovation in

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the education system. Today, any style can instantly become outdated and be enriched with new techniques. What factors determine the achievement of the desired results in the lesson? Many researchers in different countries of the world have conducted research on the application of innovations in education. Good information has been collected about “innovations”, “interactive methods”, “innovative technologies”, but there is a lack of specific recommendations for improving the effectiveness of teaching information technologies in educational institutions. Application today requires solving the following problems:

determining the specific purpose of the subject;

determining the scope and content of science;

development and recommendations of necessary educational technologies;

creation of material and technical support for science;

studying the characteristics of students;

teacher training and lesson planning.

Among the above tasks, the most important is the development of the most optimal educational technologies for organizing the educational process and their effective application in practice. Currently, there is interest in improving the effectiveness of education using interactive methods in the educational process. attention is growing every day. Classes using modern technologies are aimed at helping students find the knowledge they are acquiring, independently study and analyze it, and even draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates

conditions for the development, formation, training and education of the individual and the team.

CONCLUSION

The educational subjects of biology, natural science and geography, physics, chemistry, the fundamentals of economic knowledge, and the fundamentals of entrepreneurship are of great importance in the formation of students' scientific knowledge about nature, in the formation of their worldview, in the development of their thinking and in justifying the laws of nature. In short, the use of interactive methods contributes to the effective mastery of natural sciences and the education of comprehensively developed and accomplished individuals.

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